

WILLIAM WORDSWORTH AS THE FOUNDER OF ROMANTICISM AND HIS CONTRIBUTION TO ROMANTIC POETRY

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Abstract: The article focuses on the ideas of romanticism, its representatives and how it originated. Moreover, the contribution of William Wordsworth in romantic poetry is explored. He depicted nature in a more thorough, yet sympathetic manner in four stages which are demonstrated clearly with examples in the article below.

Key words: romanticism, romantic poetry, lyrical ballads, lake poets, romantic poetry, nature, peace.

Romanticism was a literary and artistic movement that started in Europe in the late 18th century. The movement saw the beauty of nature, emotions, and praised by artists from many walks of life, including painters, writers, poets, musicians, and singers. A new literary subgenre known as "Romantic Poetry" was born during the Romantic era. The "Romantic Age" is the time period from the late 1780s and early 1790s to the 1850s. Aside from William Wordsworth, other notable Romantic Age writers include Lord Byron, Lord Blake, Samuel Taylor Coleridge, John Keats, Percy Shelley, Walter Alva Scott, and Samuel Taylor Coleridge. After the famous collection of poems known as "Lyrical Ballads" by William Wordsworth and Samuel Taylor Coleridge was released in 1798, the history of "Romantic Poetry" as a distinct literary style may be found. Since then and up until the 1850s, the genre

saw a light reign, and many outstanding poets emerged—the most well-known of whom is still Wordsworth. The “Lake Poets” are the most well-known group to come out of the romantic poetry era. These include Robert Southey, ST. Coleridge, and Wordsworth himself. The Lake Poets were individuals who resided near lakes in northwest England, an area that is now known as the Lake District, and who extensively praised the beauty of the surrounding landscape in their separate writings.

Wordsworth is recognized as the finest Romantic poet of them all. He is actually regarded as one of the finest poets of all time. As previously stated, the genre of “Romantic Poetry” began with the publication of Wordsworth’s and ST Coleridge’s Lyrical Ballads. William Wordsworth expressed his tremendous love and regard for nature through his poems. He depicted nature in a more thorough, yet sympathetic manner. He expressed his passion for nature in four stages:

1. Love for Nature’s Physical Appearance: Wordsworth described his love for nature’s exterior appearance, such as colors, beauty, form, and so on. This is evident in Tintern Abbey, the final poem in the first edition of the Lyrical Ballads, where the poet sketches how the physical natural beauty effectively influences him.

“The day is come when I again repose. Here, under this dark sycamore, and view, These plots of cottage-ground, these orchard-tufts, Which at this season, with their unripe fruits, Are clad in one green hue, and lose themselves ‘Mid groves and copses.”

2. Admiration and Affection for Nature’s Peacefulness: It is clear from William Wordsworth’s different writings that he admired the calmness and quiet he discovered in nature. Furthermore, in some of his poems, Wordsworth expressed his longing for the peace he found in nature observation. For example, in one of his most famous pieces, Daffodils, also known as I Wandered Lonely as a Cloud, peace is represented tenderly.

“The waves beside them danced, but they Out-did the sparkling waves in

glee: A poet could not be but gay, In such a jocund company: I gazed' and gazed' but little thought What wealth the show to me had brought: For oft, when on my couch I lie In vacant or in pensive mood, They flash upon that inward eye Which is the bliss of solitude; And then my heart with pleasure fills, And dances with the daffodils."

3. Regarded Nature as a Living Soul: William Wordsworth is well-known for his love of nature. Wordsworth displays his confidence in the spirit of the cosmos, which is nothing but the soul of the earth, in his masterpiece, *The Prelude*, which also happens to be a biographical picture of his own life.

"Our birth is but a sleep and a forgetting: The Soul that rises with us, our life's Star, Hath had elsewhere its setting, And cometh from afar: Not in entire forgetfulness, And not in utter nakedness, But trailing clouds of glory do we come From God, who is our home: Heaven lies about us in our infancy!" (from "*Ode of Intimations of Immortality*" by William Wordsworth)

4. Regarded Nature as the Great Teacher of Mankind. Wordsworth, like the ancient Greek philosophers Socrates and Aristotle, thought that nature is the greatest teacher for mankind and pushed this viewpoint extensively in his works. Wordsworth states in one of his most renowned pieces, *The Table Turned*:

"And hark! how blithe the throstle sings! He, too, is no mean preacher: Come forth into the light of things, Let Nature be your teacher. One impulse from a vernal wood, May teach you more of man, Of moral evil and of good, Than all the sages can."

These lyrics vividly demonstrate Wordsworth's concentration on learning from nature. He even goes on to say that nature can teach us the difference between moralities of good and evil better than sages, a huge assertion at the time.

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